

**MAULANA ABUL KALAM AZAD
UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY,
WEST BENGAL**

MAULANA ABUL KALAM AZAD UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY (MAKAUT), formerly known as West Bengal University of Technology (WBUT), is a public state university located in KALYANI, West Bengal, India. It is funded completely by the Government of West Bengal. NH-12, HARINGHATA, Nadia, Pin- 741249, and city campus at BF-142, Sector I, Salt Lake, Kolkata 700064, <http://makautwb.ac.in>

Impact of Motivation Factors on the Employees of Airlines Industry

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HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT*

By

ARPITA MITRA

(Registration No.: 202342509210005)

Under the Supervision of

Name of Supervisor(s) DR.SOUJANYA PUDI
& co guided by PROFESSOR ASUTOSH KAR

NAME OF THE DEPARTMENT: MPhil

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the work contained in the thesis entitled ***“IMPACT OF MOTIVATION FACTORS FOR THE EMPLOYEES IN AIRLINES INDUSTRY”***, submitted by ***ARPITA MITRA (Regd. No.: 202342509210005)*** for the award of the degree of ***MPHIL*** to the ***MAULANA ABUL KALAM AZAD UNIVERSITY, WEST BENGAL*** is a record of bonafide research works carried out by him under my direct supervision and guidance.

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I certify that

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- Whenever I have used materials (data, theoretical analysis, and text) from other sources, I have given due credit to them by citing them in the text of the thesis and giving their details in the references.
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ABSTRACT

Employees play pivotal role in shaping the accomplishment expansion and even downfall of an organization. Hence there is a need for proper motivation of the employees so that they feel instigated and energized in their task that paves the way for the betterment of the organization. This analysis will predict the potency and efficacy of Human Resource Management approach and methodologies adopted by Human Resource Management of the Airlines Industries to persuade rather influencing their employees thus bestowing them with prolificacy and self -contentment about their job.

The study focuses on the action performed by Human Resource Management in stimulating the employees and recognizing several workers inspiration factors for the development of a superior organization. No matter whatever may be the circumstances ,there is consistently and invariably itsnecessary and high demand for the commitment of the staffs in Airlines Industry. Employee Motivation is of foremost important concern that affect the performance level of employees in Aviation Industry. The main concern of this research work is to bring into lime light the various facets that helps in stir up and dynamize the spirit of the employees, so that they can never feel pressurized by their work load and enjoy every bit of their job to the optimum.

Keywords:- *Employee motivation ,human resource management, performance level, employee satisfaction, organizational betterment.*

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Employees are the lifeline of any organization in sculpturing the insight within customers mind regarding any organization with their endeavor. Thus it become very much essential on the part of HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT of the organization to pacify and intensify the employee motivation so as to accomplish greater economic and non economic objective in future.

Motivation is very much essential for the employees of all sectors. However for the industries like Airlines where employees have to work under tremendous work pressure and lots of responsibilities it is of foremost important to boost up and energize the employees morale so that they feel comfortable and inspired from within and thus can easily achieve their target performance and never feel bored ,demotivated or distracted from their day to day routine task. It is really very strenuous for aviation industry carry on their job under mental pressure and always aim for enhancing their qualities to provide optimum profitability to the organization. Henceforth our recent study is to pick up those factors and bring into focus the matter which can stimulate the employees and the impact of these stimulating factors on the work performance of the employees in Airlines Industry.

A. Research Objectives:

- To analyze various factors of motivating employees in Airlines Industry
- To find out the impact of motivation on the employees of Airlines Industry

B. Statement of the Problem:

The important research question is to analyze the strategies implemented by the Human resource management and the facets that pave the way ultimately for the motivation of employees. Given below are some of the research questions need to be focused while conducting the study are as follows:

- What are the employee stimulators in the Airlines Industry?
- What are the policies and plan of actions adopted by Human resource management for energizing and inspiring the Employees of Airlines Industry?

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

- Motivated employees can bring better results as compared to unsatisfied employees. Employees perform their duty efficiently when they feel satisfied from their company (Zerbe et al, 1998). Simon and DeVaro (2006) argued that investment in developing motivated employees is an expense for the firm which will benefit the organization in the long run as it improves employee efficiency and quality of the service. Gittel, Nordenflycht, and Kochan (2004) warned that it must be kept in mind that minimizing the employee cost may lead to lower employee productivity and service quality.(ijcrb.webs.com INTERDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY RESEARCH IN BUSINESS COPY RIGHT © 2012 Institute of Interdisciplinary Business Research 531 OCTOBER 2012 VOL 4, NO 6 IMPACT OF EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION: STUDY OF AIRLINE INDUSTRY IN PAKISTAN)
- Simon and DeVaro (2006) found that companies can motivate their employees by offering good salaries, organizational culture and growth opportunities. By motivating employees towards their work companies can enhance their employee's productivity resulting as improved services and products to satisfy customer's demand.(ijcrb.webs.com INTERDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY RESEARCH IN BUSINESS COPY RIGHT © 2012 Institute of Interdisciplinary Business Research 531 OCTOBER 2012 VOL 4, NO 6 IMPACT OF EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION: STUDY OF AIRLINE INDUSTRY IN PAKISTAN)
- Motivation refers to "the reasons underlying behaviour" (Guay et al., 2010. Paraphrasing Gredler, Broussard and Garrison (2004) it is "the attribute that moves us to do or not to do something". Only when one has a generator of one's own it is possible to talk about motivation. One then needs no outside stimulation. One wants to do it.(HUMAN RESOURCES IN RYANAIR Luzmarina Kasten Viana (ufv) luzmarinakasten@yahoo.com.br)
- Motivated workers can produce better outcome in comparison with discontented employees. Employees perform better while performing assigned duties when feel contented from their organizations/ companies [7,8], highlighted that investment by any company in development of enthusiastic employees will benefit the company finally because it enhances service quality as well as employee efficiency.(Journal of Forensic Psychology urnal of Forensic Psychology ISSN: 2475-319X Open Access Volume 3 • Issue 2 • 1000138 J Foren Psy, an open access journal ISSN: 2475-319X Impact of Employee Motivation on Customer Satisfaction: Study of Airline Industry in Pakistan Shahzad N* Pakistan Army Aviation, Riphah International University, Islamabad, Pakistan, Shahzad., J Foren Psy 2018, 3:2 DOI: 10.4172/2475-319X.1000138)
- *Journal of Air Transport Management Volume 57, October 2016, Pages 184-195 Motivations and barriers for corporate social responsibility reporting: Evidence from the airline industry Author links open overlay panelTsai ChiKuoGül E. OkudanKremerbNguyen ThiPhuongaChia-WeiHsucd Innovative Techniques of Motivation for Employee Retention in Aviation Industry Neha Nazneen Siddiqui1 and Dr. Gaurav Bisaria2 1 Research Scholar, Department of Business Management, Integral University, Kursi Road, Lucknow – 226026, Uttar Pradesh, India 2 Assistant Professor, Department of Business Management, Integral University, Kursi Road, Lucknow – 226026, Uttar Pradesh, India E-mail: 1 nazneenn@iul.ac.in, 2 gaurav_or@rediffmail.com Vol. 7 • No. 1 • January 2018 ISSN: 2278-8913 (Print) ISSN: 2350-0794 (Online) DOI: 10.15410/aijm/2018/v7i1/119882*

- Motivation is derived from the key word “motivate”, the means to move ahead, encourage or influence the people to proceed for successful fulfilling a want (Kalimullah, 2010). Motivation means the encouragement by various means and modes that lead to the performance enhancement of employees in an organization. Motivation is an important part for the success of any organisation because motivated employees are more productive than the demotivated one.(Motivation in Airline Industry, organizational behaviour, march 16,2013)
- Employees are inspired by a set of factors that can exist extrinsically or intrinsically in themselves or their organizations. Performance in an organization depends on the product of motivation, ability, and environment of employees. Thus, motivation plays a major role in performance and is relevant for realizing goal-oriented behavior. (*Emirates Airline and Employee Motivation Theories*)
- Using job design to motivate employees to improve high-quality service in the airline industry(*Journal of Air Transport Management Volume 77, June 2019, Pages 17-23*)Received 19 August 2018, Revised 4 February 2019, Accepted 18 February 2019, Available online 13 March 2019, Version of Record 13 March 2019.

From the above mentioned literature review as much as I have studied so far is that Employee motivation is a most important and integral part of organization without which an organization fails to run in future. Employees who are the fuels of any organization needs to be motivated stimulated in various ways for the smooth running of an organization.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

H₀: Motivating factors has no relationship or negative relationship with employee performance

H₁: Motivating factors have positive relationship with employee performance

A. Research methods & methodological appreciation:

- The research methodologies to be used while conducting the study so far are primary and secondary research.
- The primary research however includes survey using online digital platform like Google forms to collect feedback from individuals working in Airlines Industry.
- The questionnaires are distributed and quantitative methods have been used while analyzing survey outcomes.
- Statistical tests like Cronbach's alpha, correlation coefficient, t test are conducted to analyzing data collected so far.
- For now I have mainly concentrated on Primary research, however have done literature review based on the topic from various genuine websites, journals, scholarly articles from Research gate Journal but still proper investigation of Secondary research is left over and it will be definitely conducted in future by assembling information from various research papers , research journals published earlier or from any authentic websites containing genuine information .

CHAPTER FOUR

FINDINGS OF THE RESEARCH

- The findings of the research discloses that employees of Aviation industry admit the fact that motivation factors are the main stimulating fuel behind the proper functioning of their routine work.
- According to some others opinion, it is found that various strategies are used by human resource management for motivating airlines employees such as
 - ✓ Providing Perks during layover,
 - ✓ Yearly bonus from HRTeam ,
 - ✓ BuildingYoga classes,
 - ✓ Free gym membership,
 - ✓ Departmental get together ,
 - ✓ Excursion travel
 - ✓ Gifts
 - ✓ Constant training to enforce confidence
- It is also found that sometimes employees are involved in decision making but management has a bigger say obviously.
- Generally decisions are taken by seniors and others are to be abided by the rules. But in general the employees feel very much motivated as aviation is their dream job so they enjoy every bit of this job.
- Moreover the employees feel very much interested and that is the most important stimulant for carrying on their tasks.
- Some of them find their job super challenging.
- In aviation sector employees are growing very well in their role and developing new skills day by day .
- It is everyday learning process thus adapting slowly and honing new skills so they are involved in the process of learning constantly for generating new skills.
- .When asked that how happy they feel coming to work and how focused are they on their job or duty when at work, responses from them are as follows:
 - ✓ It's a very responsible job and
 - ✓ being focused ,24x7 is the priority
 - ✓ Very much focused as without focus u can't fly
 - ✓ Very happy at work always.

Their contribution towards success of the company is the joint effort as all of them together working as a team are making things work and yes they all are contributing in a small way while doing their job with full dedication. Every effort they put leads to the contribution towards the progress of the company's goals.

CHAPTER FIVE

CERTAIN STATISTICAL TESTS BASED ON THE PRIMARY DATA COLLECTED SO FAR VIA QUESTIONNAIRES

Certain motivating factors are being provided by the human resource department to stimulate their employees. Some are discussed below:

- Employees work is being recognized directly by manager that motivates them to do their best.
- He entrusts them with high level of responsibility.
- Organization’s culture foster a comfortable, supportive work environment
- They feel that your work is seen and appreciated within your organization
- Freedom Respect and achievements gives them satisfaction in their job
- Various ways of motivation are promoted throughout, for example; employer of the month, best customer service agent, crossing the monthly quota leads to free trips, exotic adventures to contest winners, a bonus when the company supersedes the target.
- Certain statistical test called Cronbach’s alpha has been conducted to test validity of the questionnaire.Cronbach’s Alpha turns out to be 0.939012543.
- Chronbach’s Alpha is a way to measure the internal consistency of a questionnaire or survey.

The following table describes how different values of Cronbach’s Alpha are usually interpreted:

Cronbach’s Alpha	Internal consistency
$0.9 \leq \alpha$	Excellent
$0.8 \leq \alpha < 0.9$	Good
$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$	Acceptable
$0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$	Questionable
$0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$	Poor
$\alpha < 0.5$	Unacceptable

Since we calculated Cronbach’s Alpha to be 0.939 we would say that the internal consistency of this survey is "EXCELLENT"

I have conducted correlation coefficient test to test the correlation between different motivating factors (X) & their impact of motivation (Y).

The correlation coefficient of different motivating factors are as follows:

Additional perks :	0.252827992 moderate positive correlation
Perks during layout:	0.313992913 moderate positive correlation
Additional salaries	0.265372446 moderate positive correlation
Employee of the month	0.296210689 moderate positive correlation
Best customer service agent	0.29655065 moderate positive correlation
Crossing monthly quotas lead to free trips	0.313992913 moderate positive correlation

Bonus	0.335672543	moderate positive correlation
Yearly Bonus	0.231346335	moderate positive correlation
Exotic adventures to contest winners	0.313992913	moderate positive correlation
Reward yourself	0.252827992	moderate positive correlation
Team building	0.242815238	moderate positive correlation
Yoga classes	0.222026518	moderate positive correlation
Free gym membership	0.265372446	moderate positive correlation
Departmental get together	0.222026518	moderate positive correlation
Excursions	0.213465507	moderate positive correlation
Travel gifts	0.241557655	moderate positive correlation
Constant training to enforce confidence	0.335672543	moderate positive correlation

Apart from these two statistical test I have also conducted separate t test of each individual motivating factor to understand the correlation of each factor of motivation with the impact on the employee performance. The two hypothesis H0 & H1 has been formulated to prove the correlation.

Additional perks t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

H0: motivating factor additional perks have no relationship or negative relationship with employee performance

H1: additional perks have positive relationship with employee performance

As, $P(T \leq t)$ two-tail $0.000629631 < 0.05$ LOS, we accept H1, reject H0

Perks during layout t Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

H0: motivating factor perks during layout have no relationship or negative relationship with employee performance

H1: perks during layout have positive relationship with employee performance

As, $P(T \leq t)$ two-tail $0.00840675 < 0.05$ LOS, we accept H1, reject H0

Additional Salaries t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

H0: Additional salaries have no relationship or negative relationship with employee performance

H1: Additional salaries have positive relationship with employee performance

As, $P(T \leq t)$ two-tail $0.001228365 < 0.05$ LOS, we reject H0, accept H1

Best customer service agent t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

H0: best customer service agent has no relationship or negative relationship with employee performance

H1: best customer service agent has positive relationship with employee performance

As $P(T \leq t)$ two-tail $0.030274803 < 0.05$ LOS, we reject H0, accept H1

Employee of the month t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

H0: Employee of the month has no relationship or negative relationship with employee performance

H1: Employee of the month has positive relationship with employee performance

As, $P(T \leq t)$ two-tail $3.93E-13 < 0.05$ LOS, we reject H0, ACCEPT H1

Crossing monthly quotas lead to free trips t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

H0: crossing monthly quotas lead to free trips has no relationship or negative relationship with employee performance

H1: this factor has positive relationship with employee performance

As, $P(T \leq t)$ two-tail $0.008460775 < 0.05$ LOS, we reject H0, accept H1

Bonus t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

H0: BONUS has no relationship or negative relationship with employee performance

H1: this factor has positive relationship with employee performance

As, $P(T \leq t)$ two-tail $0.01574774 < 0.05$ LOS, we reject H0, accept H1

Yearly Bonus t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

H0: yearly BONUS has no relationship or negative relationship with employee performance

H1: this factor has positive relationship with employee performance

As, $P(T \leq t)$ two-tail $0.000158501 < 0.05$ LOS, WE REJECT H0, ACCEPT H1

Exotic adventures to contest winners t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

H0: exotic adventures to contest winners has no relationship or negative relationship with employee performance

H1: this factor has positive relationship with employee performance

As, $P(T \leq t)$ two-tail $0.008460775 < 0.05$ LOS, we reject H0, accept H1

Reward yourself t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

H0: reward yourself has no relationship or negative relationship with employee performance

H1: this factor has positive relationship with employee performance

As, $P(T \leq t)$ two-tail $0.000629631 < 0.05LOS$, we reject H0, accept H1

Team building t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

H0: team building has no relationship or negative relationship with employee performance

H1: this factor has positive relationship with employee performance

As, $P(T \leq t)$ two-tail $5.48401E-08 < 0.05LOS$, we reject H0, accept H1

Yoga classes t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

H0: yoga classes have no relationship or negative relationship with employee performance

H1: this factor has positive relationship with employee performance

As, $P(T \leq t)$ two-tail $0.000158501 < 0.05LOS$, we reject H0, accept H1

Free gym membership t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

H0: free gym membership has no relationship or negative relationship with employee performance

H1: this factor has positive relationship with employee performance

As, $P(T \leq t)$ two-tail $0.001228837 < 0.05LOS$, we reject H0, accept H1

Departmental get together t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

H0: departmental get together has no relationship or negative relationship with employee performance

H1: this factor has positive relationship with employee performance

As, $P(T \leq t)$ two-tail $7.78E-05 < 0.05LOS$, we reject H0, accept H1

Excursions t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

H0: excursions have no relationship or negative relationship with employee performance

H1: this factor has positive relationship with employee performance

As, $P(T \leq t)$ two-tail $7.77E-05 < 0.05LOS$, we reject H0, accept H1

Travel gifts t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

H0: travel gifts have no relationship or negative relationship with employee performance

H1: this factor has positive relationship with employee performance

As, $P(T \leq t)$ two-tail $0.00031825 < 0.05$ LOS, we reject H0, accept H1

Constant training to enforce confidence t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

H0: constant training to enforce confidence has no relationship or negative relationship with employee performance

H1: this factor has positive relationship with employee performance

As, $P(T \leq t)$ two-tail $0.01574874 < 0.05$ LOS, we reject H0, accept H1

CHAPTER SIX

RESEARCH PLAN

A. Research Plan

I have planned categorically to move on with the research work.

- To prepare questionnaire in the form of Google form
- The questionnaires are distributed the same among the individuals working in Airlines Industry.
- Have taken as much as sample for interviewing.
- Have reviewed the feedback given by the interviews
- Have conducted various statistical tests like Cronbach's alpha, correlation coefficient, t test with the primary data collected.

B. Conclusion

The motto of this research work is to bring the matter into limelight that how important is employee motivation and also the value and importance of the strategies formulated and implemented by Human resource management in strengthening the employees' morale thus contributing for the greater benefit of the organization. Here enlie the importance of the research and the potential impact the study is to know understand and analyze the factors that are foremost essential for motivating the employees in Airlines industry and the effect of employee motivation on their performance level as well.

CHAPTER SEVEN

FUTURE SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

There are certain areas which can be explored further in future research work Those issues that are experience by employees in the workplace like

- Salaries are big issue .
- Ego clashes
- Lack of proper sleep,
- Angry passengers or customers,
- Drinking abuse violence,
- Time constraint scheduling.

Further in depth studies and analysis can be done to know the causes behind such issues and adequate measures can be suggested to deal with such problems so that they may not recur in future.

QUESTIONNAIRES

(Primary Data)

The questionnaires prepared so far are in the form of Google form containing questions for interview from employees in Airlines Industry are given below:

- Q1. What motivating factors are being provided at your Airlines?
- Q2. What are the strategies used by HR to motivate employees of your Airways? OR What are the strategies used by HR Management?
- Q3. What are issues that are experience by employees in the workplace?
- Q4. Whether Employees are involved in Decision Making As Much As Possible?
- Q5. In general, how motivated do you feel at work?
- Q6. How stimulating do you find day-to-day tasks?
- Q7. How inspired do you feel by your work goals?
- Q8. How well do you think you're growing in your role and developing new skills?
- Q9. How happy do you feel coming to work and how focused are you on your job or duty when at work?
- Q10. How much do you feel you're contributing to the success of the company?
- Q11. How well do you feel your work is recognized directly by your manager that motivates you to do your best?
- Q12. Does he entrusts you with high level of responsibility?
- Q13. How would you rate your overall job satisfaction?
- Q14. How likely would you be to recommend a job here to a friend?
- Q15. How secure do you feel in your job?
- Q16. Whether your job is challenging and exciting?
- Q17. Does your organization's culture foster a comfortable, supportive work environment?
- Q18. How you feel that your work is seen and appreciated within your organization?
- Q19. What gives you satisfaction in your job?
- Q20. How job satisfaction improves your performance?

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